

EFFECTIVE APPROACHES EMPLOYED BY ELEMENTARY TEACHERS IN CHRISTIAN SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT

This study concentrated on identifying optimal teaching practices for elementary educators at Central Balili Wesleyan Academy Inc., employing a qualitative research design with interviews as the primary data collection method. Key findings revealed that teachers utilized differentiated instruction, inquiry-based approaches, and technology integration. Factors influencing effective teaching included the learning environment, student characteristics, teacher unpreparedness, time constraints, physical stamina, individual student differences, and a lack of instructional materials. Challenges during lessons included learner disinterest, discipline issues, short attention spans, unprepared students, and the influence of students' siblings. Conclusively, differentiated instruction emerged as the most frequently employed strategy, while most identified factors were considered controllable. Notable challenges were learner disinterest, discipline problems, students' limited attention spans, unpreparedness, and the impact of students' siblings, highlighting prevalent obstacles in the instructional process.

Keywords: *Best practices, strategies, differentiated instruction, factors, controllable, physical stamina*

INTRODUCTION

Teachers wield a substantial influence on the academic achievement gap, acknowledged as the most critical factor by the State of Vermont (2013). The quality of teachers and their preparation, training, and support significantly impact student achievement (NCATE,

2010). While future teachers have commendable role models, the evolving global environment necessitates continuous improvement in teaching practices. "Best practices" encompass learning principles, strategies, and methods based on comprehensive standards, such as differentiated instruction, inquiry-based approaches, and technology integration, aiming to support diverse learners and enhance overall student success (Darling-Hammond, 2010; Marzano, 2008).

Research underscores the pivotal role of teachers in shaping effective education, with effective instructional practices linked to positive educational outcomes (Hattie, 2009; Emmer & Stough, 2001). Proposals for teaching reform in the United States emphasize a departure from traditional methods towards modern approaches, including cooperative group work and questioning, proven to elevate student achievement (Zemelman et al., 2005; Bietenbeck, 2011). Effective teaching practices involve close monitoring, well-structured lessons, and informative feedback, fostering a positive impact on student achievement (Brophy & Good, 1986; Wang et al., 1993). Additionally, professional competence and teacher characteristics play crucial roles, influencing instructional practices and, subsequently, student outcomes (Shulman, 1987; Talis, 2009; Grossman et al., 2013).

In the contemporary educational landscape, the traditional model of passive learning through lectures is deemed less effective, with a shift towards more interactive, applied, and student-centered methods (Khursid & Ansari, 2012; Teo & Wong, 2000). The literature highlights the importance of teacher-student relationships, the use of effective instructional strategies, and a shift from reactive to preventive classroom management strategies for fostering a conducive learning environment (Pianta et al., 2009; Lane et al., 2011; Manzano et al., 2003). Recognizing the significance of these issues, the study at Central Balili Wesleyan Academy Inc. aims to contribute to the enhancement of educational practices and the meaningful learning experiences of students.

Whitehurst (2001) outlines nine standards for best practices in education, emphasizing the importance of empirical evidence in decision-making for effective instructional delivery. These standards include a clear and common focus, high standards and expectations, strong leadership, supportive and personalized learning, parent/community involvement, monitoring, accountability, and assessment, aligned curriculum instruction, professional development, and flexible time and structure. These standards aim to create a conducive learning environment where teachers, administrators, students, and parents share common goals, maintain high expectations, and actively engage in collaborative efforts to improve student performance.

Baker (2019) contributes strategies for educators specializing in special education, incorporating techniques such as scaffolding, modeling, prompting, and differentiated instruction. These strategies focus on adapting instruction to diverse learning needs through multiple texts, supplementary materials, varied activities, task and product design, independent learning contracts, group investigations, negotiated criteria, and learning contracts. Recognizing that teaching styles directly impact effectiveness and job satisfaction, Djigic & Stojiljkovic (2011) highlight the importance of evaluating and

adopting appropriate teaching styles. They reference Baumrind's (1971) four teaching styles – authoritative, authoritarian, indulgent, and permissive – with an emphasis on the authoritative style for its association with positive student behaviors, independence, warmth, and social competence. Understanding the impact of teaching styles, along with effective methods and strategies, is crucial in addressing challenges faced by teachers and in implementing best practices at Central Balili Wesleyan Academy Inc.

Research Questions

The main objective of the study assessed the best practices towards achieving the desired results of maximum and quality learning.

Specifically, the study sought the answers to the following questions.

1. What are the teaching strategies utilized by the teachers?
2. What is the extent of influence of the factors affecting the best practices of elementary teachers?
3. What are the problems encountered in the conduct of your lesson?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research adopted a qualitative approach, specifically employing the phenomenological method, utilizing interviews as the primary data gathering procedure. Leonard (2018) emphasizes that phenomenological research aims to understand how individuals experience specific events, employing interviews, observations, and surveys. In this study, a semi-structured, in-depth interview technique was employed to investigate the best practices for elementary teachers at Central Balili Wesleyan Academy Inc. This method, aligned with the phenomenological model, involves conducting intensive individual interviews with a limited number of respondents to delve into their perspectives on a particular idea, program, or situation (Boyce, 2006). The choice of this research technique allows for the collection of detailed and nuanced information directly from the teachers at Central Balili Wesleyan Academy Inc.

Research Locale and Participants

The investigation took place at Central Balili Wesleyan Academy, Inc. throughout the academic year 2020-2021. The study encompassed all nine elementary teachers employed at Central Balili Wesleyan Academy, Inc., constituting a total enumeration of the participants involved in the research.

Research Instrument

The primary instrument employed for data collection in this study was the constructed interview guide questions, serving as a structured framework during formal interviews. Comprising three distinct parts, the interview guide focused on eliciting information regarding the teaching strategies employed by the teachers, the magnitude of influence

exerted by factors impacting classroom management best practices for elementary teachers, and the severity of problems encountered in implementing these best practices. The interview guide played a pivotal role in steering the researcher through the interview process, ensuring systematic and comprehensive exploration of the key aspects related to the study's objectives.

Data Collection Procedure

The researcher obtained permission to conduct the study from the Dean of the Graduate School at Baguio Central University. Before proceeding with the formal interviews, explicit authorization was sought from the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Benguet, or their designated representative. Upon receiving approval, the researcher personally conducted formal interviews using group chats and individual discussions within the school setting. Following the completion of the formal interviews, the researcher proceeded to analyze and interpret the gathered responses. This meticulous process of obtaining permissions and conducting interviews in accordance with established protocols enhances the ethical and procedural integrity of the research study.

Data Analysis

This qualitative study aims to explore elementary teachers' perspectives on best practices, seeking insights into effective strategies for improving learning. One-on-one semi-structured interviews were conducted using a guide with three parts focusing on teachers' utilized strategies, the extent of factors influencing best practices, and problems encountered during lessons. The gathered data were transcribed and analyzed in accordance with the interview guide, organizing and tallying responses to discern recurring themes. The research intends to provide a nuanced understanding of teacher perspectives, shedding light on the most impactful practices, factors shaping them, and challenges encountered in the realm of elementary education.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Teaching Strategies Used in the Conduct of Class

Table 1 presents the teaching strategies employed by teachers at Central Balili Wesleyan Academy, with a focus on three prominently mentioned strategies: inquiry-based instruction, differentiated instruction, and technology utilization. The majority of interviewed teachers emphasized the use of differentiated instruction, tailoring methods according to learners' diverse abilities and learning areas. Following Howard Gardner's Multiple Intelligences Theory, various approaches were employed for different learner types, such as visual-spatial, bodily-kinesthetic, musical, linguistic, naturalistic, intrapersonal, and interpersonal learners. However, despite its effectiveness in catering to individual needs, teachers faced challenges in implementing differentiated instruction due to the time-intensive nature of creating diverse activities for each student. This struggle aligns with Good's (2006) study, highlighting the overwhelming pressures

teachers face daily, making it challenging to address the individual needs of diverse learners adequately.

The second most used strategy among teachers was technology utilization, acknowledging the dominance of technology in the 21st century. Teachers recognized the motivational impact of technology-rich lessons, keeping learners engaged and interested in the learning process. However, challenges surfaced regarding accessibility, especially for those still learning to operate gadgets or lacking resources for online learning. The pandemic further underscored the significance of technology for safety but revealed its limitations for certain students. The third prominent strategy identified was inquiry-based learning, fostering a deeper understanding by involving students in the learning process. Despite its benefits, teachers encountered issues with varying learning paces and the direct involvement of parents in teaching. These findings imply that each strategy has its advantages and challenges, impacting either the teacher or the learners, reinforcing the complex nature of implementing effective teaching practices.

Factors That Affect the Best Practices of Teachers

Numerous factors impact the best practices of teachers, including the learning environment, unpreparedness of learners, limited time for each learner, physical stamina of both teachers and learners, and individual differences. The learning environment emerges as a significant factor, particularly in today's context where learning often takes place in learners' homes. Disruptions caused by passing cars, noisy neighbors, and cluttered, non-conducive environments pose challenges for both teachers and learners. The unpreparedness of learners, ranging from their absence or engagement in other activities upon the teacher's arrival, diminishes the teacher's enthusiasm. Limited time allocated to each learner, only three hours per week, results in rushed lessons, unused visual aids, and incomplete coverage of subjects.

The physical stamina of teachers, who travel to learners' homes due to pandemic restrictions, and learners engaged in pre-lesson work affect the overall teaching dynamic. Fatigue hampers the teaching experience, impacting both the teacher's performance and the learners' receptiveness. Individual differences among learners, although sometimes alleviated by teaching multiple students simultaneously, introduce a new challenge of accommodating varied learning paces. The findings underscore that, despite employing diverse teaching strategies, teachers grapple with numerous factors affecting their best practices, with some elements within their control and others beyond their influence, creating a complex interplay between teacher and learner experiences.

Problems Encountered in Conducting the Lesson

The teachers at Central Balili Wesleyan Academy encountered several challenges during the conduct of their lessons, as revealed in the interviews. These challenges include the unwillingness of pupils to learn and listen, disciplinary issues, disturbances caused by learners' siblings, learners with short attention spans, and concerns related to learners' personal hygiene. The unwillingness of pupils to engage in the learning process poses a significant obstacle, as even dedicated and effective teaching efforts may prove futile

without active cooperation from the learners. Teachers expressed difficulties redirecting learners' attention during lessons, with some engaging in distracting behaviors such as playing or being absent-minded.

Disciplinary issues emerged as another prominent problem, with teachers constrained in their ability to address unruly behavior due to parental sensitivities. Parents often resist teachers' efforts to discipline their children, limiting the teachers' actions during the teaching process. Disturbances caused by siblings at home were also noted, as they interrupted learners during discussions, sought attention, or hindered concentration. Additionally, some learners' neglect of personal hygiene, leading to unpleasant odors, affected the teachers' ability to concentrate on teaching.

A crucial issue identified was the short attention span of certain learners, a common challenge in education. Learners with short attention spans often get bored easily, play during lessons, or lose focus, resulting in limited learning. While not all aspects affecting attention span are controllable, efforts to involve learners and minimize distractions can enhance focus. Overall, the findings underscore the multifaceted nature of the problems encountered during lessons, affecting both teachers and learners and highlighting the role of parents in shaping the teaching and learning environment.

Conclusions

The study's conclusions are derived from its findings, highlighting three key points. Firstly, among the three mentioned teaching strategies, differentiated instruction emerged as the most widely utilized during class instruction. Secondly, a majority of the identified factors influencing teaching practices were found to be within the realm of control. Lastly, the study identified several problems encountered during lesson delivery, including learners' lack of interest, discipline issues, students with short attention spans, unpreparedness, and disturbances caused by students' siblings. These findings underscore the significance of effective teaching strategies, controllable factors, and challenges faced by educators during the instructional process.

Recommendations

Based on the study's conclusions, recommendations include the adoption of differentiated instruction by teachers as it effectively meets the individual needs of each learner. Given the controllable nature of most identified factors, it is advised to develop effective plans targeting these manageable elements. Moreover, collaboration among teachers, parents, and learners is encouraged to collectively address encountered problems, fostering a successful and meaningful teaching and learning process.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher demonstrated exemplary conduct throughout the study, adhering to research standards by employing appropriate language, methodologies, and comments. Initial steps involved obtaining permission from relevant authorities within the university

and the Division of Benguet, whose endorsement paved the way for data collection. Clear communication about the study's purpose was provided to respondents both verbally and through a letter accompanying the survey guide. The respondents were assured of their autonomy to choose which interview questions to answer. To ensure confidentiality, responses were treated with utmost privacy, and respondents were randomly approached for follow-up interviews. The researcher sought explicit permission for the utilization of respondents' responses for the study's intended purpose. In the subsequent analysis, interpretation, and discussion, the researcher maintained objectivity and impartiality, transitioning seamlessly from respondents' individual experiences to the broader universal essence of the subject under consideration.

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